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Report on the 2nd Granada Workshop: Implementing Effect Biomarkers

Additional Deliverable Report

AD14.5

WP14 - Biomarkers of Effect

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1 Ongoing publications and activities within WP14

1.1 AOPs and effect biomarkers: phthalates and reproductive effects

Author: Kirsten Baken (VITO)

A strategy to support exposure-effect relations in biomonitoring studies was presented with the validation of selection of effect biomarkers for reproductive effects of phthalates as a proof of concept. We combined biomarkers of reproductive effects previously associated with phthalates exposure in human observational studies to mechanisms of action and events reported in experimental studies, as well as to adverse reproductive outcomes using information collected in existing Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs). This exercise resulted in effect biomarkers for the family of phthalate compounds with substantial mechanistic support that may causally link phthalate exposure to adverse reproductive outcomes and help build the weight of evidence of phthalate toxicity in humans. It also identified novel biomarkers for early biological response which may result in adverse reproductive outcomes. The activation of PPAR α , PPAR γ , and GR may initiate events leading to impaired male and female fertility as well as other adverse effects of phthalate exposure. Therefore, these receptors appear as promising targets for the development of effect biomarkers. This study is a proof of concept to join epidemiological, experimental, and toxicological information in order to advance the field of Human Biomonitoring and has been recently published in Environmental research (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2019.05.013>).

A strategy to validate a selection of human effect biomarkers using adverse outcome pathways: Proof of concept for phthalates and reproductive effects

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1.2 Effect biomarkers on bisphenols

Authors: Shereen Cynthia (INSERM) and Vicente Mustieles (UGR)

The manuscript under preparation based on the selection of effect biomarkers for bisphenols, after the literature revision made by some partners from WP14, was presented. The plan and the novelty of this bisphenols revision was highlighted in this talk. The Introduction of this article describes the approach that was used to define an effect biomarker in a Human Biomonitoring context, and this was based on the conceptual framework proposed by the National Research Council (NRC) as given below.

After conducting the Pubmed literature revision selecting six health endpoints, biomarkers of effect were identified from the retrieved articles, and the AOP framework that is given below was used to classify these biomarkers as molecular or biochemical, based on their biological level of organisation.

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In the Results and discussion section of the revision article, an overview of all molecular and biochemical biomarkers identified in epidemiological studies is presented. Knowledge gaps were also identified in two areas through this literature search- neurodevelopment and reproduction. Three promising biomarkers were prioritised for biomonitoring purposes: BDNF as a biomarker for neurodevelopment, gene expression of some nuclear receptors for reproduction and kisspeptin for puberty. These prioritised biomarkers were tentatively placed in AOP-like framework. The perspectives section of the manuscript discusses the importance of OMICS techniques in novel biomarker identification for Human Biomonitoring purposes.

1.3 Effect biomarkers for Cr and Cd

Authors: Maria Joao (INSA) and Claudia Gundacker (MUW)

A literature survey was performed for chromium (VI) [Cr(VI)], in order to create an inventory of available biomarkers of effects for this specific exposure. The results of that survey, following the criteria previously established in D14.1, were presented. The traditional effect biomarkers most frequently used in epidemiological studies included oxidative stress (e.g., malondialdehyde) and genotoxicity (e.g., micronucleus analysis) markers. Among the novel effect biomarkers, those relying on gene expression and epigenetic effects (e.g., DNA methylation analysis) were identified as the most informative and having the potential to improve specificity and generate high throughput data. However, they are expensive and still need to be further developed and validated for that purpose. This information, together with the inventory of available biomarkers of effects for cadmium (Cd) exposure, gathered from the literature searches performed for (Cd), is being summarising in a revision paper under the title: "Biomarkers of effect for hexavalent chromium and cadmium in Human Biomonitoring studies: A comprehensive review" (in preparation). The corresponding Decision Memo for this publication has already been presented and approved by the MB. The first draft will be circulated among co-authors in the first week of July (the submission is planned for October 2019 to Environmental Research journal).

Additionally, the multicentre study on occupational exposure to Cr(VI) compounds was briefly presented, focusing the effects biomarkers that are planned to be analysed by several laboratories: micronuclei in peripheral blood leukocytes and in reticulocytes, biomarkers of oxidative stress in urine, global genome methylation and telomere length.

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1.4 Effect biomarkers of combined activity to chemical mixtures

Authors: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo (UGR)

Human populations are commonly exposed to complex low-dose chemical mixtures that can interact between them, leading to additive, antagonistic and/or synergistic effects. Thus, the prediction of their consequences on human health is one of the current challenges of environmental health, considered among HBM4EU objectives.

Inside WP14, five different ex-vivo cell-based assays have been conducted in order to evaluate the biological responses of a mixture of lipophilic halogenated compounds, previously extracted from 24 placentas from the Spanish INMA-Granada cohort. The chosen bioassays were: i) E-screen, ii) ER-reporter gene assay, both used to assess the estrogenicity of the mixture; iii) AR-reporter gene assay, to measure the anti-antagonistic activity; iv) Aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AhR-CALLUX), to evaluate the induction/inhibition of the aforementioned receptor; and v) the Xenopus Embryo Thyroid Assay (XETA) to evaluate the thyroid activity induced/inhibited by the mixture.

The mixture of halogenated compounds elicited signals for estrogenicity, anti-androgenicity, induction/inhibition of the AhR activity and the inhibition of the thyroid activity at varied degrees. These type of biomarkers of combined activity could be an efficient and complementary strategy for the evaluation of complex real-world environmental chemical mixtures in human samples. Additionally, their implementation could be of added value for HBM programs. A manuscript reporting and integrating these results is under preparation.

Distribution of biomarkers of combined biological activity performed within WP14: E-screen (UGR), ER-reporter gene assay and AR-reporter gene assay (AU), AR-reporter gene assay and AhR-CALLUX (DTU) and the XETA (CNRS).

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1.5 Isolation and measurement of combined activity of PFAS mixtures from human placentas, and Review on PFAS exposure and Thyroid homeostasis in epidemiological studies

Author: Eva Cecilie Bonfeld-Jorgensen (AU)

A. Isolation and measurement of combined activity of PFAS mixtures from human placentas

AU has developed a methodology to extract and fractionate the real mixture of PFAS from human serum samples. This WP14 partner had earlier demonstrated that these PFAS components had xenoestrogen activities. In 702 pregnant Danish women they demonstrated that PFAS induced xenoestrogenic transactivity was significantly inverse related to birth weight, length and head circumference (published in EHP, January 2019; doi/10.1289/EHP1884).

AU has further developed this methodology to isolate the combined mixture of PFAS from placenta homogenate sample provided by UGR from the Spanish INMA-Granada cohort, and measured the xeno-estrogenic transactivity. Similar as for serum samples, they found that 52% of the placenta extracts significantly induced xeno-estrogenic transactivity and 68% extracts further enhanced the transactivity of the natural estrogen receptor ligand (Estradiol - E2). Currently, AU is developing the method for serum extraction and measurement of the combined PFAS mixture induced xeno-androgenic transactivity.

B. Review on PFAS exposure and Thyroid homeostasis in epidemiological studies

AU has conducted a review on “Exposure to PFAAs and Thyroid homeostasis in epidemiological studies”. Maternal Thyroid Hormones (TH) are essential for fetal brain development in early gestation and PFAAs are suggested to interfere with maternal TH in the second or third trimesters. Hypothyroidism during pregnancy can lead to delays in growth and intellectual development in the baby. A literature survey was performed for PFAAs, in order to create an inventory of available biomarkers of effects for Thyroid homeostasis. Eleven studies were selected and included, seven studies on mothers and 6 studies on infant PFAS exposure, respectively. PFAAs exposure may cause hypothyroid state in mother and infant. However, future studies are needed to uniform the method of examining the associations across studies. The corresponding Decision Memo for this publication has already been presented and approved by the MB.

1.6 Review on organophosphate flame retardants

Authors: Marina Lacasaña, Beatriz González Alzaga and Antonio Hernández (EASP)

During the workshop, EASP expressed their interest to broad their previous literature search on organophosphate flame retardants, to also include organophosphate pesticides based on their similar molecular structures.

A systematic review of biomarkers of effect for organophosphate flame retardants (OPFRs) compounds in relation to all selected endpoints (neurotoxicity, reproductive disorders, immunotoxicology...), was conducted and coordinated by EASP. The results of this search were presented in the 2018 workshop of WP14 and included in deliverable 14.2. Briefly, WP14 partners identified 23 studies (in vivo and vitro studies) conducted in humans wherein these biomarkers were measured. Most of these studies assessed traditional biomarkers, such as thyroid hormones, oxidative stress, neurodevelopmental outcomes, or even clinical effects. However, due to the limited number of studies, they deemed that the scientific interest of a specific paper for OPFRs was rather low.

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Nevertheless, considering the long experience of this research team working on OP pesticides, they proposed a new approach to cover OPFRs. The EASP proposal is to write a joint paper with all the selected biomarkers of effects for OP compound, including FRs and also OP pesticides. The reasoning for grouping these two set of compounds is because they have similar molecular structures and the scarce literature on human studies addressing biomarkers of effect related to OPFR, which is not the case for OP pesticides. EASP believes that a review on OP compounds (FR and pesticides) can be more timely and complete, and more attractive to be published. All partners discussed this proposal during the workshop deciding which partners be involved in the review of literature on pesticides, and all agreed to continue with the proposal.

1.7 Review on PAHs

Author: Anne T. Saber (NCRWE)

During the workshop, NCRWE and INSA discussed the possibility to include part of the information obtained in WP14 literature search, regarding effect biomarkers for PAHs, coordinated by NCRWE, in an ongoing PAHs paper revision focused on occupational studies (INSA) in collaboration with WP8. Since that meeting the co-authors have approved it and the PAH article is in progress and will be circulated by the coordinator (INSA team) in July 2019.

1.8 Lessons learned and next steps

Author: Vicente Mustieles (UGR)

- All together HBM4EU partners have learned that a major goal of HBM research is the measurement of both exposure and effect biomarkers, to better understand the potential impact of environmental exposures on human health.
- The inventory of effect biomarkers (D14.3) based on all the literature searches conducted for the first list of prioritised substances (D14.2), has been crucial for the selection of first set of proposed effect biomarkers for implementation in the HBM4EU aligned studies, as well as in European existing cohorts.
- The interaction of WP14 with other HBM4EU WPs (mainly WP8, WP10, WP11 and WP13), has been fundamental for achieving a well-orchestrated proposal for the implementation of these effect biomarkers in HBM4EU aligned studies.

WP14 has also learned from the **Literature searches** on effect biomarkers for the 1st set of prioritised chemical compounds: each search is different and needs to be planned based on the specific chemical family under study. Nevertheless, some common points have been observed among the different searches and revisions made within WP14:

- i) **Summary** of effect biomarkers that have been more frequently employed
- ii) **Novel biomarkers**, including the omics field
- iii) Identification of **gaps in knowledge**
- iv) **Experimental support** of effect biomarkers based on mechanistic studies and/or AOPs.

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Inside WP14 (D14.4 and AD14.4) we have also the opportunity to conduct some **Pilot Cases-Studies** that may serve to:

- Advance in the knowledge of biomarkers of combined effect in a “real-world” chemical mixture present in human samples.
- Fine-tune methodologies for the implementation of the selected effect biomarkers to be implemented in the aligned studies, such as for example DNA methylation, urinary 8OHdG, steroid hormones, untargeted metabolomics and many other markers that will be of interest for the aligned studies.
- Additionally, these pilot cases-studies, using samples from established European cohorts, can also help to fine-tune the measurement of markers of interest for the aligned studies (BDNF in serum or urine, storage conditions, variability, selectivity, among of biological sample needed, etc.).
- Identify partners with specific technical capabilities

Next Steps for 2019-2021

The literature searches for the 2nd set of prioritised substances has already started and it aims for:

- Be less general and more specific than those made for the 1st list of prioritised substances, especially in the case of chemical families extensively studied (i.e., heavy metals).
- Oriented towards a peer-review publication from the beginning
- The selection criteria for effect biomarkers need to be based on the available experimental support (AOPs), preclinical nature and predictive potential.
- Therefore, the searches are being adapted according to i) the chemical family; b) the most important adverse outcomes of interest; c) the existence of *a priori* gaps in knowledge obtained from previous review works; d) novel biomarkers will be prioritised; e) experimental support and/or AOP data will be gathered for the most promising effect biomarkers found.

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2 Preliminary results from the literature searches for the second set of prioritised substances

2.1 Pesticides

Authors: Shereen Cynthia (INSERM) and Carmen Freire (UGR)

In this talk, the Pesticide Literature Revision (2nd set of prioritised substances) was summarised, recently initiated with the collaboration of UGR, INSERM, VITO and CNRS, WP14 partners. The search was conducted for six individual and/or pesticide families emphasised in Deliverable 14.3., i.e., pyrethroids, chlorpyrifos and dimethoate, glyphosate and fipronil. The six health endpoints that were prioritised for the first set of prioritised chemicals were also considered in this literature search as well. However, the need of modifications of terms for each of the selected health endpoints, to reflect the disease outcomes related to each of these pesticides, is under discussion.

Pyrethroids were classified as ‘Approved for use’ or Non-Approved for use’ inside the European Union, in order to prioritise the literature search. The four partners involved have had discussions earlier to create a categorical search plan, and it was suggested to prioritise the pesticides based on the annual production rate in Europe, and also to include terms related to pesticide metabolites/commercial names. A preliminary search was conducted to retrieve the data from epidemiological studies on children’s exposure in Europe. From the preliminary search, 1139 human studies were identified for Pyrethroid family, 350 studies for Chlorpyrifos, 41 for Dimethoate, 203 for Glyphosate and 36 studies for Fipronil for the six health endpoints.

2.2 Lead

Authors: Anne T. Saber (NCRWE) and Claudia Gundacker (MUW)

Developmental neurotoxicity has been chosen as the focus of the literature search on Lead, because this endpoint seems to be the most critical effect at low doses of exposure (EFSA, 2010).

NCRWE and MUW have performed an initial literature search in PubMed (27.03.2019) using the following search terms: (((("lead") OR "pb") OR lead[MeSH Terms]) OR "plumbum"[Title/Abstract]) OR "7439 92 1"[EC/RN Number]) and neurodevelopment. This resulted in 596 references in total. This search was followed by a sorting process to exclude the references in which the term “lead” was only used as a verb and not as metal. This reduced the number of references to approximately 160 articles.

160 abstracts sorted for relevance

Ineligible

- No biomarker of effect examined
- Focus was on other neurotoxicants
- Abstract uninformative/Paper not accessible
- Animal experiments

Eligible (24)

- One or more biomarker examined
- In vitro experiments on human cells included (candidate genes indicated)

The 160 references were further sorted according to relevance. The inclusion criteria were that one or more biomarkers were examined in relation to a neurodevelopmental outcome associated to

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lead exposure. NCRWE and MUW also included *in vitro* data when information on candidate genes was indicated. This resulted in 24 eligible references that were grouped according to biomarker significance. NCRWE and MUW will now continue this work with these selected references and also consider the use of Yale Mesh terms as discussed at the Granada WP14 meeting in April 2019, developed and proposed by Stephan Couderq (PhD student at CNRS). As a result, NCRWE and MUW have expanded the Mesh term list to get a complete picture of (epi-)genetic effects that modulate lead exposures.

2.3 Mercury

Authors: Jean-Baptiste Fini and Stephan Couderq (CNRS) together with (UCY)

The National French Research Center (CNRS) and University of Cyprus (UCY) are working on the literature search dealing with mercury and related biomarkers of effect. Stephan Couderq (PhD student at CNRS) developed a method to fine-tune search terms for additional novel epigenetic or OMICs biomarkers using Yale's Mesh term analyser, and another to remove overlapping articles between different health-endpoints. By now, CNRS provided a tutorial to the partners working on lead and to the pesticides group, in which CNRS participates. However, note that this method could be applied to all compounds as it prioritises articles containing novel biomarkers, and permits a significant reduction in the total articles needed to be treated.

For example, when CNRS applied the method to the mercury search, they first obtained:

	Neurobehavior	Cancer	Endocrine diseases	Immunology/ Allergy	Metabolic/ Cardiovascular	Reproduction	TOTAL
Mercury/methylmercury - related articles	Humans: 859	Human: 257	Humans: 142	Human: 269	Humans: 1124	Humans: 643	Humans: 3294
	Animals: 578	Animal: 85	Animals: 150	Animal: 205	Animals: 1466	Animals: 550	Animals: 3034

Whereas after applying the method they reduced the amount by 25%, obtaining a final list of unique articles pertaining to one specific or multiple health endpoints:

	Unique articles
Mercury/ Methyl mercury - related articles	Humans: 2438
	Animals: 2309

Mercury is a known neurotoxicant. WP14 involved partners were quite surprised to see that the majority of health endpoints were linked with metabolic and cardiovascular endpoints. CNRS has expertise in neurobehavior and thyroid hormones, and consequently is interested in the neurobehavioral effects of mercury (first column). UCY is more interested in cancer in relation to mercury (second column). During the Granada workshop, Dr. Argelia Castaño (ISCI leader) mentioned that Dr. Diaz (ISCI) would be interested in covering metabolic and cardiovascular health endpoints, which she has since confirmed.

2.4 Arsenic

Author: Kirsten Baken (VITO)

Health endpoints of arsenic to be included in the literature search were prioritised based on 1) the Scoping document, 2) the WP13 strategy to address policy questions for 2nd list of HBM4EU priority compounds (AD13.1), 3) evidence of a causal association according to the National Research Council (2013), and 4) relevance for the aligned studies, in which arsenic is foreseen to be measured in teenagers:

Health outcome	Scoping document	WP13 strategy	NRC (2013)	Aligned studies
Neurodevelopment	✓			✓
Obesity and metabolic disorders (focus on diabetes)	✓			✓
Cardiovascular diseases (including ischemic heart disease and hypertension)	✓		✓	
Cancer (focus on lung, bladder, skin)	✓		✓	
Endocrine diseases		✓		✓
Allergies and immunological diseases				✓
Reproductive diseases	✓			

A preliminary search resulted in the number of publications displayed below. Inclusion of 'MMA' and 'DMA' (abbreviations for the most common human metabolites) in the 'Arsenic' search term appeared to have obscured the results. Next steps will be to perform the searches without 'MMA' and 'DMA' and further prioritise and divide the health endpoints based on the number of publications, as well as knowledge gaps and susceptible groups identified in literature reviews.

Health outcome	All results	<10 years	No review	'Arsenic' in abstract
Neurodevelopment	1298	679	620	89
Diabetes	2065	996	949	264
Cardiovascular	649	317	287	39
Cancer	181	87	85	31
Endocrine	270	117	113	23

Birgitte Lindeman (**NIPH WP14 partner**) expressed their interest to participate in this literature search during the Granada workshop.

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2.5 UV-filters

Authors: Vicente Mustieles (UGR) and Anne Marie Vinggaard (DTU)

Lead: UGR (Vicente Mustieles, Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo and Mariana F. Fernández)

WP14 partners: DTU (Anne Marie Vinggaard, Camilla Taxvig, Marta Axelstad Petersen)

WP13 partners: Region H (Anna Maria Andersson and Hanne Frederiksen)

Benzophenone-3 (BP-3) is an organic ultraviolet (UV) filter widely used in sunscreens, body lotions and make-up, but also in many other applications including plastics and textiles (Morrison et al., 2017). The potential endocrine disrupting properties of BP-3, together with its ubiquitous exposure in human populations have led to an increasing concern about its use (Frederiksen et al., 2017). Therefore, we aimed to conduct a comprehensive review covering all the references related to: i) human sources of exposure; ii) human levels of BP-3 in pregnant women, children, adolescent and adults; iii) human exposure-health associations, including both health endpoints and the effect biomarkers that have been previously implemented. In addition, we also aimed to group all the *in vitro* and *in vivo* experimental references conducted in vertebrates (fish and rodents), in order to review the experimental support for specific outcomes, as well as to evaluate potential mechanisms of action and the xenometabolism and tissue disposition of BP-3.

In order to achieve this objective, we have used the search terms “Benzophenone-3 OR oxybenzone OR 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzophenone”, which provided 782 references. After selecting the PubMed filter “Full-text”, the number of references was reduced to 719. The titles and abstracts of these 719 references were screened and classified in the abovementioned groups. A flow-chart with the included and excluded articles is being prepared. Then, we will integrate data from human populations (sources of exposure, exposure levels by window of development, effect biomarkers and health endpoints, and toxicokinetic data from human intervention studies), and will summarise the most interesting *in vitro* and *in vivo* experimental information from animal models. Finally, gaps in knowledge and promising novel effect biomarkers will be presented and discussed.

- Morrison GC, Bekö G, Weschler CJ, Schripp T, Salthammer T, Hill J, Andersson AM, Toftum J, Clausen G, Frederiksen H. *Dermal Uptake of Benzophenone-3 from Clothing. Environ Sci Technol.* 2017;51(19):11371-11379. doi: 10.1021/acs.est.7b02623.
- Frederiksen H, Nielsen O, Skakkebaek NE, Juul A, Andersson AM. *UV filters analyzed by isotope diluted TurboFlow-LC-MS/MS in urine from Danish children and adolescents. Int J Hyg Environ Health.* 2017;220(2 Pt A):244-253. doi:10.1016/j.ijheh.2016.08.005.

2.6 Mycotoxins

Authors: Maria Joao (INSA) and Ludek Blaha (MU)

Mycotoxins are secondary metabolites produced by some fungi species that widely contaminate food and feed commodities. Human exposure to mycotoxins occurs mainly through the ingestion of contaminated food, although inhalation may also be a relevant exposure route in occupational settings. In the HBM4EU project, two mycotoxins' groups will be addressed: Fumonisin, particularly, FB₁ and Deoxynivalenol (DON). Background information about exposure to these mycotoxins, health endpoints and effect biomarkers was presented during the workshop.

Preliminary general information about exposure, mechanisms of action, health endpoints and effect biomarkers for FB₁ and DON was presented during the workshop:

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Mycotoxins: Fumonisin B1 (FB₁) and Deoxynivalenol (DON)

Based on that information, and taking into account the policy questions regarding this substance group, the first step will be to search for “DON or FB1 and effect biomarkers” in epidemiologic studies. Furthermore, participating WP14 partners proposed to focus the literature searches on the following topics:

- FB₁ and biomarkers of hepatotoxicity, nephrotoxicity, and carcinogenicity
- DON and biomarkers of immunotoxicity, reproductive toxicity and endocrine disruption
- Exposure and effect biomarkers in the general population, children (vulnerable group) and workers
- Co-exposure or aggregate exposure to mycotoxins and combined or mixture effect biomarkers.

In a second step, and in order to address the health endpoints of more concern, and link them to AOPs, literature searches should include mechanistic *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies and key events, e.g., FB₁ and adducts, DNA repair inhibition, mutagenicity or genotoxicity.

2.7 Acrylamide

Authors: Marieta Fernández (UGR)

Acrylamide is a chemical present in a wide range of everyday foods, mainly in starchy food products as a result of cooking practices at high-temperature (>120°C) (frying, baking, roasting), but also in some food industrial processing, when sugars and amino acids food products are present. Acrylamide is also present in non-food industrial chemical and in tobacco smoke.

In 1994, International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) classified acrylamide as ‘probably carcinogenic’ to humans. Acrylamide is absorbed in the gastrointestinal tract and distributed to all organs where it is extensively metabolised [mainly as Glycidamide (GA), principal responsible of the genotoxicity and carcinogenicity of acrylamide]. Several expert panels [IARC, EFSA’s Panel on

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Contaminants in the Food Chain (CONTAM)] have confirmed that acrylamide potentially increases the risk of developing human adverse health effects (such as neurotoxicity, adverse effects on male reproduction, developmental toxicity and carcinogenicity) for all consumers in all age groups. However, children are considered the highest exposed age group on a body weight basis. Although evidence from animal studies confirms that acrylamide and its metabolite glycidamide are genotoxic and carcinogenic, epidemiological data is still limited and inconclusive.

Current levels of dietary exposure to acrylamide usually reaches 1 µg/kg body weight daily, although in high consumers and occupationally-exposed subjects, exposure levels could exceed 8 µg/kg of body weight per day. The European Commission has recommended to keep acrylamide levels as low as possible and to monitor acrylamide levels in food. Additional initiatives inside Europe include the assessment of dietary exposure to acrylamide, evaluation of the toxicological hazards and characterisation of the potential risks to human health.

WP14 partners are working on the literature search dealing with acrylamide and biomarkers of effect. By now, UGR has found a limited number of articles related with this issue, based on the following search strategy:

"Acrylamide"[Mesh] AND "Neurotoxicity Syndromes"[Mesh] (45 articles); "Acrylamide"[Mesh] AND "Carcinogenicity Tests"[Mesh] (17 articles); "Acrylamide"[Mesh] AND "Mutagenicity Tests"[Mesh] (100 articles); "Acrylamide"[Mesh] AND "Reproduction"[Mesh] (109 articles); and "Acrylamide"[Mesh] AND "Oxidative Stress"[Mesh] (81 articles). Additionally, Pubmed search with "Acrylamide" AND ("reproductive" OR "endocrine" OR "oestrogen" OR "testosterone" OR "hormonal" OR "endocrine disruption") captured 206 references.

3 Progressive implementation of both traditional and novel effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies

Authors: Kirsten Baken (VITO) and Vicente Mustieles (UGR)

Within HBM4EU task 8.1, Human Biomonitoring studies are being aligned to result in comparable chemical exposure data with EU wide coverage. Currently, analysis of the first set of priority chemicals is planned. A proposal, jointly prepared by WP 8, WP 9, WP 10, WP 11, WP 13, and WP 14, to additionally implement a selection of health outcome parameters (anthropometric measurements or assessed via questionnaires), classical clinical biomarkers of effect as well as novel effect biomarkers relevant for these chemicals (as emerged from literature searches performed in WP13 and WP14) in the HBM4EU aligned studies was presented and discussed. The workshop participants supported the proposal to perform a proof of principle to show the added value of effect biomarkers to increase the weight of evidence of exposure-effect associations in human observational studies. Advantages of combining traditional and novel as well as early and late biomarkers of effect were identified. It was concluded that the implementation of effect biomarkers could be conducted with limited additional resources for post-harmonisation of available health outcome data or for new analyses of biomarkers of effect. The outcomes of the workshop were integrated in a Decision Memo for the Management Board and presented at the MB meeting of May 6th.

An overview of the proposed effect biomarkers per chemical and age group is presented below.

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4 Implementation of effect biomarkers in established European cohorts, and specific pilot cases-studies

4.1 Case-study on pesticides (WP15 interaction)

Authors: Aldert Piersma (RIVM) and Mirjam Luijten (RIVM)

Although the partner RIVM was not able to attend the Second Granada Workshop, WP14 has proposed this specific interaction with WP15: One of the case studies included in WP15 is a field-study to assess exposure to pesticides in five European countries. WP14 has invited RIVM (lead of WP15 and partner collaborator in WP14) to consider the possibility of assessing potential biomarkers of effect in this pesticide case-study during the remaining two years of the project (2020-2021). Although the literature search on pesticides will provide the best evidence, WP14 has recommended considering the implementation of 8OHdG and 8-isoprostane biomarkers in urine, based on the following points:

1. Oxidative stress caused by pesticides has been recognised as an important mechanism through which many of the pesticides may exert their harmful effects (Sabarwal et al., 2018).
 2. These markers can differentiate between DNA damage and lipid peroxidation.
 3. Urine is the best biological matrix for the assessment of these oxidative biomarkers (when adjusted for urine dilution).
 4. These oxidative markers have been previously proposed as biomarkers of the effect to chemical mixtures (Silins and Hogberg, 2011), and the focus is to assess the potential effect to pesticides mixtures.
 5. Several associations have been previously reported with these markers in small-sized studies, so this case study offers the opportunity to replicate or contradict previous findings.
 6. Although these oxidative effect biomarkers are not specific of a given disease (it can be predictive of cancer, obesity and cardiovascular disorders), it would represent a very nice add that would be of great help to evaluate if exposure to pesticides at those levels measured in the survey, can potentially be associated with adverse health effects.
- Sabarwal A, Kumar K, Singh RP. Hazardous effects of chemical pesticides on human health- Cancer and other associated disorders. *Environ Toxicol Pharmacol.* 2018;63:103-114. doi: 10.1016/j.etap.2018.08.018.
 - Silins I, Högberg J. Combined toxic exposures and human health: biomarkers of exposure and effect. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2011;8(3):629-47. doi: 10.3390/ijerph8030629.

RIVM has proposed to the Management Board in a Decision Memo that was presented at the MB meeting of 26-28 June 2019 to perform *in vitro* experimental work on per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) with the aim to strengthen and validate certain effect biomarkers from human studies (identified in WP14). These studies will provide important mechanistic information that is currently lacking and are expected to be a valuable contribution to the project, since they will greatly enhance the creation of AOP networks (WP13) and provide input for policy-related questions (WP5).

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Exposure to per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) such as PFOS and PFOA, has consistently been associated with changes in lipid metabolism and perturbed homeostasis of triglycerides and cholesterol in humans; however, despite huge attention on identifying adverse outcomes in relation to PFASs exposure, detailed mechanistic understanding of the health effects observed is lacking. RIVM in collaboration with WP13 are planning to publish a peer-reviewed manuscript to show a detailed overview of the state-of-the-art regarding knowledge of the mechanisms involved in relation to PFASs and homeostasis of triglycerides and cholesterol. This overview is key to better understand the mechanisms involved and to identify current gaps in knowledge, as well as essential to guide experimental work to fill the existing gaps in knowledge.

4.2 The case-study on antiandrogenic chemical mixtures (WP15 interaction)

Author: Anne Marie Vinggaard (DTU)

Male reproductive health and fertility is currently in the spotlight: sperm quality is low and continually decreasing in many countries, there is a higher demand for assisted reproductive techniques, more and more boys are born with malformed sex organs and the incidence of testicular cancer is increasing. The cause is hypothesised to arise during fetal life and to be partly due to exposure to 'antiandrogenic' chemicals. Therefore, the aim of this case study will be to evaluate the potential for a human health risk due to the present exposure to complex mixtures of 'anti-androgenic' chemicals based on our current knowledge.

DTU has so far identified 231 compounds on a 'gross' list for antiandrogenic effects in vitro and collected hazard data. UGR, together with the collaboration of UBA, are going to find European human exposure data. Based on these data, mixture effects will be evaluated using the hazard index, after definition of realistic exposure scenarios.

4.3 BDNF in urine and serum samples from the INMA-Granada as a pilot case study

Author: Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo (UGR)

Brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF), is a growth factor from the family of neurotrophins that plays an important role in neurogenesis, synaptic transmission and brain development (Bathina and Das, 2015; Lu et al., 2014). BDNF has also been implicated in neuropsychiatric disorders that affect behaviour (Autry and Monteggia, 2012) and changes in the expression of BDNF have been reported in several neurodegenerative diseases, such as Alzheimer disease, Parkinson disease and Huntington disease (Zuccato and Cattaneo, 2009). Therefore, it is an ideal candidate as a novel biomarker of neurodevelopment within HBM4EU.

- Bathina S, Das UN. Brain-derived neurotrophic factor and its clinical implications. *Arch Med Sci.* 2015;11(6):1164-78. doi:10.5114/aoms.2015.56342.
- Lu B, Nagappan G, Lu Y. BDNF and synaptic plasticity, cognitive function, and dysfunction. *Handb Exp Pharmacol.* 2014;220:223-50. doi:10.1007/978-3-642-45106-5_9. Review.
- Autry AE, Monteggia LM. Brain-derived neurotrophic factor and neuropsychiatric disorders. *Pharmacol Rev.* 2012;64(2):238-58. doi: 10.1124/pr.111.005108. Review.
- Zuccato C, Cattaneo E. Brain-derived neurotrophic factor in neurodegenerative diseases. *Nat Rev Neurol.* 2009;5(6):311-22. doi: 10.1038/nrneurol.2009.54. Review.

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For the fine tuning of BDNF quantification, UGR is developing the methodology for two different biological human samples: serum and urine. For serum, just around 20µL of volume is needed and its measurement is feasible with an ELISA immune assay. Urine BDNF can also be measured with an immune assay but with a previous acidification and extraction of the samples and with a sample-volume around 1.5ml.

To verify that this novel effect biomarker can be used in the aligned HBM4EU studies, UGR will measure BDNF in serum and urine samples from the Spanish INMA-Granada cohort at two different time-frames: 9-10 years and 16-17 years and will assess its predictive potential for behavior and cognitive data available from this study population. BDNF methylation will also be assessed in serum samples of this cohort by INSERM.

Strategy to implement BDNF as a novel effect biomarker in the INMA-Granada cohort

4.4 Epigenetic measurements in Pélagie cohort:

Author: Shereen Cynthia (INSERM)

A proof of concept study, involving INSERM and EHESP participation, has carried out on human placenta samples from two existing European birth cohorts (INMA and PELAGIE). INSERM has performed epigenetics, metabolomics and metal analyses in 25 placenta samples from the Spanish INMA cohort and in 40 placenta samples from the French PELAGIE cohort. For epigenetic studies, they measured the levels of H2AX by using Western blot. The INMA samples showed varying levels of gamma H2AX and they did unsupervised clustering of samples that showed the presence of 4 clusters of samples with low to high gamma H2AX levels. For PELAGIE placenta samples, they did unsupervised clustering and observed two groups of samples with low and high gamma H2AX levels. INSERM also measured Chromatin immunoprecipitation (ChIP) for the histone mark, H3K4me3 that is associated with actively transcribing genes. They observed clustering pattern showing that *BDNF*, *ESRRA*, *H2AFX*, and *PGR* have significant H3K4me3 occupancy in the promoters when compared with low DNA damage group INMA samples. DNA methylation analysis of BDNF in bisulfite-converted INMA DNA samples showed 4 clusters with different melt temperature. Sanger sequencing of these samples confirmed the presence of methylation at CpG nucleotides in the CREB region of BDNF Exon IV region in some of the INMA

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samples. Currently, INSERM is standardising the techniques to conduct epigenetic analysis in frozen whole blood samples. Moreover, INSERM has collaborated with statisticians to combine analysis of metabolomics, epigenetics and metal data that was generated from different studies.

4.5 Novel proposal to assess biomarkers of neural damage in the GENEIDA birth cohort (EASP-ISCIII)

Authors: Marina Lacasaña (EASP-ISCIII). Determination of molecular biomarkers of brain damage in samples from the established Spanish GENEIDA (Genetics, Early Life Environmental Exposures and Infant Development in Andalucía) birth cohort.

The GENEIDA study is a prospective birth cohort currently ongoing. It started in 2014 in the region of Poniente (Almería, Southeast Spain), one of the largest intensive agriculture areas in Spain and Europe (25,000 hectares of plastic greenhouses). In this cohort, 800 women were recruited during the 12-13 week of gestation (first trimester of pregnancy), and then followed-up during the second and third trimesters, childbirth and at different ages during childhood (children are currently being monitored at the age of 4 years).

The objective of the GENEIDA birth cohort is to evaluate the effect of exposures to environmental contaminants (e.g. pesticides, organophosphorus flame retardants, metals, and some other endocrine disruptors, etc.) and lifestyles (e.g., diet, stress, etc.) on growth and development over the fetal stage, childhood and adolescence. An additional objective is to evaluate the interaction between prenatal environmental exposures and lifestyles on the epi/genome (e.g., transcriptome, methylome, microRNA, metabolome, and microbiome) and their impact on health at different life stages. So far, a set of biological samples properly collected and stored at -80°C is available:

- Mother during pregnancy: Serum, plasma, whole blood, urine, nails, hair and stool
- Delivery: Placenta (stored within RNAlater TissueProtect Tubes and standard tubes), cord blood (serum, plasma, whole blood, whole blood-RNAlater).
- Children (1, 2 and 4 year-old): urine, feces, nails, hair.

Currently EASP has data on the urinary concentrations of 6 dialkyl phosphates (metabolites of organophosphorus pesticides) during pregnancy. Also, they have got financial support to analyse the dialkyl phosphate metabolites in urine samples from children at 12 and 24 months of age, as well as metabolites of pyrethroids and organophosphate flame retardants in urine samples of mothers during pregnancy and of their children at the same time-points.

In addition, we have data on different biomarkers of effect, such as thyroid hormones (TSH, free T3 and free T4) in maternal serum, cortisol in the mothers' hair, placenta methylome, ano-genital distance in infants, and cognitive and neurobehavioral function tests at different ages: 12, 24 months, and 4 years. Over 2019, they have planned to determine biomarkers of immunotoxicity in the mother's serum during pregnancy and in cord blood, including cytokines, chemokines and growth factors.

One of the key advantages of the GENEIDA birth cohort is the current availability of a large number of biological samples to determine biomarkers of effect. These cover from pregnancy to children 4 years of age, which means that biomarkers can be measured longitudinally over pre- and postnatal stages. EASP has put at the WP14/HBM4EU disposal, biological samples for the determination of biomarkers of nervous system damage during the different stages, such as the BNDP (proposed as novel biomarker of effect), which can be complemented by other molecular biomarkers of: a) neuronal damage (e.g., hyperphosphorylated neurofilaments –pNF-H–, a

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biomarker for axonal injury and degeneration); b) myelin damage (e.g., myelin basic protein – MBP–, a biomarker of myelin sheath disruption); and c) glial cell damage (protein S100B, a calcium-binding protein abundant in astrocytes, or glial fibrillary acidic protein –GFAP–, a biomarker of astrogliosis, which consists of a cellular reaction that indicates both neuronal and glial damage).

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5 Work justification and Future Steps

Author: Marieta Fernández (UGR)

The strategy to support exposure-effect relationship, to be implemented in the HBM4EU aligned studies, as well as in some ongoing HBM4EU case-studies, and in certain European existing cohorts, has already been presented, including a strategy for the selection of effect biomarkers for specific chemicals, health outcomes and window of exposure (i.e., biomarkers of reproductive effects associated with phthalate exposure in children/adolescents), as a proof of concept. The first inventory of effect biomarkers (D14.3) related to the 1st set of prioritised chemical compounds, based on the extensive literature searches conducted, has been crucial for the consolidation of this strategy. As a result, a proposal to implement novel molecular and some more traditional clinical effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies is ongoing, as a proof of principle to test the hypotheses that implementation of specific effect biomarkers to enhance the interpretation of exposure biomarker measurements and increase the weight of evidence of exposure-health outcome associations in human observational studies.

All WP14 partners have learned that one of the major goals of HBM research is the measurement of both exposure and effect biomarkers, to better understand the potential impact of environmental exposures on human health. They have also learnt that the interaction of WP14 with other HBM4EU WPs (mainly WP8, WP10, WP11 and WP13), is the key for achieving a well-orchestrated proposal for the implementation of these effect biomarkers inside HBM4EU.

WP14 has decided that the literature searches on effect biomarkers for the 2nd set of prioritised chemical compounds, already ongoing, needs to be based on the specific chemical family under study. Some common points need to be followed for the different searches and revisions made within WP14. Those are: i) The literature searches for the 2nd set of prioritised substances should try to be less general and more specific than those made for the 1st list of prioritised substances, especially in the case of chemical families extensively studied (i.e., heavy metals). 2) Oriented towards a peer-review publication from the beginning; 3) the selection criteria for effect biomarkers need to be based on the available experimental support (AOPs), preclinical nature and predictive potential; and 4) the searches adapted according to i) the chemical family; b) the most important adverse outcomes of interest; c) the existence of *a priori* gaps in knowledge obtained from previous review works; d) novel biomarkers will be prioritised; e) experimental support and/or AOP data will be gathered for the most promising effect biomarkers found.

We all have two and half exciting years of research and knowledge ahead of us.